

1. Introduction

The growing integration of Renewable Energy Sources (RES) in the electricity grid has reduced the flexibility of the current power system, due to the inherent stochastic and intermittent character of these RES [1]. A lack of flexibility in a system can lead to negative effects like difficulty balancing demand and supply, renewable energy curtailments or price volatility [2]. To avoid these issues, new sources of flexibility must be deployed.

At the same time, the grid is experiencing a growth in the number of existing microgrids, formed by Distributed Energy Resources (DER), like Solar Photovoltaic (PV) installations, battery storage systems, Electric Vehicles (EV) or smart home appliances [3]. These microgrids and their participants can become central actors in the electricity grid by using demand-side management actions to increase the flexibility of the system. In this way, demand, that was often treated as relatively inelastic, can help to reduce the variability and uncertainty introduced by the RES [4]. In addition, emerging concepts like the Internet of Things and new actors, like the Demand Aggregator (DA), allow to intelligently control the demand of small customers, allowing them to actively participate in the electricity system [5] reducing their electricity bill and contributing towards a successful energy transition.

For this reason, demand-side flexibility and demand aggregation, have received substantial attention in the research world. The studies found on the literature provide high value into understanding the potential for flexibility of different assets and their interaction with DAs. However, these studies are mainly based either on simulations [6] or on real-life trials [7].

This work makes use of the valuable middle ground that is a laboratory environment. In comparison with simulations, laboratories allow for more realistic scenarios with real power flow, while not depending on uncontrollable factors, like weather conditions, that affect real-life trials. In addition, in view of the restrictions that are still present in many flexibility markets that limit the presence of DAs [8], having a tool for the experimental assessment of different Demand Response (DR) actions can be useful to gain knowledge before real-life implementations.

The goal of this work is to create a platform for the experimental testing of demand-side flexibility actions, controlled by a DA. The microgrid laboratory of the Catalonia Institute for Energy Research (IREC) has been integrated with the Bamboo Energy aggregation platform [9]. With the defined platform, two scenarios have been developed to test the environment created and analyse the flexibility potential of different customer types.

The current document is divided as follows: Section 2 describes the laboratory environment of IREC. Section 3 present the methodology used to integrate the laboratory with the aggregation platform and define the scenarios to be developed. The results of these scenarios are shown in Section 4 along with the discussion in Section 5. Finally, Section 6 finalizes the document with the conclusions extracted from the study.

2. Description of the microgrid laboratory

The laboratory of IREC, from now on SmartLab, is a microgrid laboratory that combines both real and emulated devices. The Smartlab, working up to 200 kVA, is used for developing and testing hardware and software elements. This section contains a brief description of its electrical and communication schemes.

2.1. Electrical scheme

A general scheme of the SmartLab is shown in Figure 1. The laboratory includes additional emulation devices and storage systems that have not been used in this work and thus are not represented. The laboratory microgrid can be directly connected to the grid or to the grid emulator device. All the different elements available in the SmartLab are connected in parallel to the laboratory busbar. Out of these elements, the emulation cabinets and real elements, in particular the second-life battery, are of interest for the current work.

Figure 1. Electrical scheme of the Smartlab

2.1.1 Emulation cabinets

The laboratory operation is based on the hardware emulation approach, which allows for real physical equipment to be operated under a broad range of scenarios without depending on the real occurrence of the boundary conditions suitable for the experimental validation. Inside the SmartLab there are 5 B2B-uX-4kW emulation cabinets. Each unit is composed of two AC/DC converters in back-to-back configuration, which can work as active rectifiers or active inverters, allowing a bidirectional power flow. Therefore, the cabinets can act as generating or consuming nodes. This way, it is possible to reproduce the power profile of different elements like batteries, solar PV panels or a household consumption, for example. Figure 2 shows the converters of the emulation cabinets in the back-to-back connection. The converters' operating voltage is 400V and they are connected through a DC bus of 700V. Each emulation cabinet contains a Local Controller (LC), which is a Raspberry Pi3 device.

Figure 2. Laboratory emulation cabinet diagram

The converter on the microgrid side is called the emulator and controls the maximum active power by imposing a voltage on the DC bus. The second converter, located on the grid side, is the Active Front End (AFE). The AFE receives start/stop messages, active and reactive power references, and it is requested information about status and measurements. The AFE injects or consumes power from the grid, based on the reference value received. As a generator, the emulator drives power from the grid to the DC bus and as a load, it drives power from the DC bus to the grid [10].

2.1.1 Second-life battery

The second-life battery located in the Smartlab previously belonged to a Renault Kangoo EV. After its service in the vehicle, the battery is now employed in the laboratory as a static storage system for potential second-life application testing [11]. The battery pack is equipped with a Battery Management System and a 40 kVA inverter. This electronic system is aware of the internal state of the battery and is able to output that data via CAN Bus. In the same way, it is also able to receive information from the exterior through the same bus and communicate the maximum power that the battery is able to charge or discharge. The battery set-up is shown in Figure 3.

Figure 3. Laboratory second-life battery

2.2. Communication scheme

The communication between the different elements in the SmartLab happens hierarchically in three levels: top, middle and bottom layer. On the bottom level we find the power converters of the different elements of the SmartLab and on the middle layer the Local Controllers of each element of the lab. In the top layer, the microgrid can interact with the high-level control which is the Supervisory Control And Data Acquisition (SCADA) system. The communication between the LCs and the power converters is done via CAN Bus and allows the LCs to send setpoints to the converters, change their state and read the current operating conditions. Between the LCs and SCADA Modbus TCP-IP over Ethernet cables is used. The SCADA is responsible for the definition, control and monitoring of the scenarios to be developed.

3. Methodology

3.1 Integration of the Smartlab into the aggregation platform

An overview of the control scheme for the current project is shown in Figure 4. The DA acts as the highest level of control, on top of the SCADA, by sending flexibility activations that can overwrite the setpoints defined from the SCADA. The communication between the DA and SCADA is configured, in a first instance, via the aggregator API. However, due to the growing interest on implementing open communication protocols, the OpenADR protocol has also been tested as an alternative way to communicate with the aggregator.

To be able to interact with the DA, three actions are required, which are described in detail in the following sections:

1. The microgrid must be defined before starting the interaction, including the elements that form it and their main characteristics.
2. Periodically, with a frequency depending on the requirements from the DA, relevant information of the state of the different assets must be sent.
3. The DA defines flexibility activations for certain assets that are read from the SCADA and must be translated into commands to the laboratory assets.

Figure 4. Communication hierarchy of the flexibility platform

3.1.1 Definition of the microgrid

Although in future works additional elements from the SmartLab could be integrated, as a first step two emulation cabinets acting as a PV and a load, the second-life battery, a virtual HVAC and a virtual load have been chosen for the set-up. The main characteristics of these elements are described in Table 1.

Element	Type	Controllable	Characteristics
HVAC	Virtual	Yes	Max Power: 1.5 kW Num of thermal zones: 1 COP: 3.5
Thermal Zone	Virtual	-	Num of temperature sensors: 1 Area of windows: 4 m ² Wall resistance: 5 °C/kW Inertia: 3 kWh/°C
PV	Emulated	No	Max Power: 4 kW
Battery	Real	Yes	Capacity: 5 kWh Max Power: 10 kW Max SoC: 80 % Min SoC: 20 %
Load 1	Virtual	No	Max Power: 1.5 kW Min Power: 0 kW
Load 2	Emulated	No	Max Power: 3.1 kW

Table 1. Definition of the microgrid elements

The laboratory cabinets allow to emulate only electrical behaviours. Since the thermal part is necessary to evaluate the indoor temperature of the thermal zone, a simulation has been built. A RC model has been defined to simulate the temperature variations in a thermal zone of a building. These type of models are grey-box models, which are used for building modelling due to the good trade-off between computational speed and accuracy they offer [12]. The model uses a RC network to represent the heat transfer mechanisms that occur inside a building [13]. For the model

developed, the change in temperature inside the thermal zone is a combination of the following factors (as represented in eq. 1): solar gains through the windows, thermal power provided by the HVAC and heat conduction through the walls from/to outdoor.

$$T_i = T_{i_0} + \frac{T_{a_0} - T_{i_0}}{Ra \cdot Ci} \Delta t + \frac{Aw \cdot Ps}{Ci} \Delta t + \frac{COP \cdot P}{Ci} \Delta t + c \quad (1)$$

where

T _i : indoor temperature at the end of the period (°C)	Δt: duration of the period (s)
T _{i₀} : indoor temperature at the beginning of the period (°C)	Aw: area of windows (m ²)
T _{a₀} : ambient temperature (°C)	Ps: solar radiation (kW/m ²)
Ra: thermal resistance of the walls (°C/kW)	COP: efficiency of the HVAC (-)
Ci: building inertia (kWh/°C)	P: electric power of the HVAC (kW)
	c: random noise (-)

In addition, the power output of the HVAC, which is an input to the thermal model, is calculated through a control model that follows the temperature setpoint. The power required from the HVAC is proportional to the difference between the indoor temperature and the setpoint. In addition, the machine follows a hysteresis, between a maximum and minimum temperature delta over the setpoint, to avoid constant jumps of on/off states.

The battery charge and discharge is controlled through a control model with the goal of maximizing the self-consumption factor [14]. In addition, security grid charges are defined after the battery remains in minimum State of Charge (SoC) for a specific time. This avoids having the battery in low values of SoC for too long, which considering the self-discharge of the battery could create issues.

3.1.2. Status of the assets

Once the microgrid starts operating, information regarding the state of the microgrid assets must be sent so that the DA can estimate the potential flexibility. This information includes the following fields for each asset:

- Active Power (W)
- Status, which indicates if the asset is on (1) or off (0)
- Quality, which indicates if the information is good (1) or if there has been an error (0)
- State of Charge (%), for the battery only
- Temperature (°C) of the thermal zone, for the HVAC only

3.1.3. Flexibility activations

For the controllable assets of the microgrid (HVAC and battery), the DA sends flexibility activations. Depending on the type of asset, the activation received contains different information:

- HVAC: temperature setpoint for the thermostat.
- Battery: power setpoint.

3.2 Definition of the scenarios

Two scenarios have been defined and developed in order to test the flexibility platform. The scenarios represent use cases where two customer types interact with the aggregator for a period of three days, receiving flexibility activations which modify the consumption of the household. For each one, the base case has been first developed, with no interaction with the aggregator. Then, the communication with the aggregator has been allowed in order to see how these customers would be affected by the commands received. A graphical representation of the scenarios is given in Figure 5 and a summary of the cases and the elements of each scenario in Table 2.

- **1 - Residential.** This customer has a HVAC inside a thermal zone that can be controlled for obtaining flexibility and an uncontrollable load (Load 1) that represents other consumptions (lighting, appliances...). Both summer and winter periods have been considered. In the base case two temperature setpoints are defined: one for the day to achieve thermal comfort (22°C) and the other for the night to reduce the HVAC consumption (24°C for the summer and 19°C for the winter). In the aggregator case, the DA can overwrite the temperature setpoint, within the limits fixed by the users [-2 °C; +2 °C] to modify the HVAC consumption. This scenario makes use only of virtual systems (the HVAC and the Load 1). The inputs for this scenario (outdoor temperature, solar radiation and electrical load) have been extracted from real data of a tertiary building and scaled to represent a single household.
- **2 - Prosumer:** this customer has a self-consumption system formed by a PV, a second-life EV battery and an uncontrollable load (Load 2). In this case, only a summer period has been considered with days of more or less clouds to add variability. The goal of this scenario is to analyse how the battery charge and discharge power can be modified by the aggregator. The base case only uses the battery control defined according to the PV generation and the load consumption. In the aggregator case, the setpoints calculated by the battery control can be overwritten by the activations received. This scenario makes use of two of the emulation cabinets (for emulating the PV and the load) and of the second-life battery. The inputs for this scenario (PV generation and electrical load) have been extracted from real data of a tertiary building and scaled to represent a single household.

Figure 5. Diagram of both scenarios developed

Type		Assets				Cases			
		PV	Battery	HVAC	Load	Base Summer	Base Winter	Aggregator Summer	Aggregator Winter
1-Residential	Simulated			1.5kW	1.5kW	X	X	X	X
2-Prosumer	Emulated/Real	4kW	5kWh		3kW	X		X	

Table 2. Summary of the scenarios

To quantify the effect of the aggregator in the customers, different Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) have been extracted from literature [15,16] and from the ones used by the aggregator:

- KPI1: Total energy consumption change. Measures the reduction or increase of the energy imported from the grid over the three days of the test, as shown by Eq. 2 where EI is the imported energy.

$$KPI1 = \frac{EI_{aggregator} - EI_{base}}{EI_{base}} * 100 \quad (2)$$

- KPI2: Total energy cost change. Measures the reduction or increase of the cost over the three days of the test. To evaluate the cost of the electricity bill, the average of the Spanish Voluntary price for the small consumer (PVPC) with two periods, during the days of test (year 2020) [17] has been considered. For the prosumer scenario, the surplus energy is sold at a price obtained from the regulated values [18]. The equation for KPI2 is shown in Eq. 3, where C is the cost of electricity.

$$KPI2 = \frac{C_{aggregator} - C_{base}}{C_{base}} * 100 \quad (3)$$

- KPI3: Load reduction. Measures the change in the power consumed during the events defined by the aggregator. KPI3 is calculated with Eq. 4 where P_{DR} is the average power measured during the DR events.

$$KPI3 = \frac{P_{DR,aggregator} - P_{DR,base}}{P_{DR,base}} * 100 \quad (4)$$

- KPI4: Rebound effect. Quantifies the rebound effect, that is, the additional energy consumed following a flexibility activation [19]. This KPI, as given by Eq. 5, compares the energy consumed during the hour after an event is finished (E_{rebound}) between the base and aggregator cases.

$$KPI4 = \frac{E_{rebound,aggregator} - E_{rebound,base}}{E_{rebound,base}} * 100 \quad (5)$$

- KIP5: Reliability index. Gives an indicator of whether the user has successfully received the activations or not by measuring the 30-minute intervals in which the correct setpoint was read from the aggregator, as per Eq. 6.

$$KPI5 = \frac{\text{Intervals with correct setpoint}}{\text{Total number of intervals}} * 100 \quad (6)$$

- **KPI6: Thermal comfort level (only for 1-Residential).** Measures the thermal discomfort, defined as the amount of intervals that the indoor temperature exceeds the comfort of the users (19°C to 24°C) during events and rebound periods, as per Eq. 7.

$$KPI6 = \frac{\text{Intervals out of comfort}_{\text{aggregator}} - \text{Intervals out of comfort}_{\text{base}}}{\text{Intervals out of comfort}_{\text{base}}} * 100 \quad (7)$$

- **KPI7: Self-consumption factor change (only for 2-Prosumer).** Measures the change in the self-consumption factor (SC, given by Eq. 9) between the aggregator case and the base case, defined as the percentage of load that has been covered by the PV system, directly from it or from the battery. KPI7 is calculated using Eq. 8.

$$KPI7 = \frac{SC_{\text{aggregator}} - SC_{\text{base}}}{SC_{\text{base}}} * 100 \quad (8)$$

$$SC = 1 - \frac{\text{Electricity imported}}{\text{Electricity consumed}} \quad (9)$$

4. Results

4.1. Scenario 1 – Residential

Figure 6 shows the results for the scenario 1 – Residential, for the summer case. On the top, the power consumed by the HVAC and on the bottom the indoor temperature of the thermal zone. Green lines represent the results of the base case (normal consumption, without the interaction of the aggregator) and red ones represent the case where the aggregator sends activations. As shown in Table 3, during the three days of the test, a total of 5 activations were received for the summer, at different hours (morning, midday or afternoon), with duration of 30 or 60 minutes and all with a setpoint of 23.5°C. Thus, in all the activations, the HVAC was forced to follow a temperature setpoint of +2°C in respect to its normal consumption in the base case.

Period	Activation	Setpoint	Day	Start	Duration
Summer	S1	23.5°C (+2°C)	1	08:00	30 min
	S2	23.5°C (+2°C)	1	18:30	30 min
	S3	23.5°C (+2°C)	2	12:00	1 h
	S4	23.5°C (+2°C)	3	08:00	1 h
	S5	23.5°C (+2°C)	3	18:00	1 h

Table 3. Activations received for Scenario 1 - Residential (summer)

- Activation S1: the first activation received took place early in the morning, when the thermostat changed from the night setpoint (24°C) to the day one (22°C). The aggregator overwrote this 22°C setpoint and defined one of 23.5°C. Since the setpoint was higher than in the base case, the HVAC reduced the power consumed. However, the indoor temperatures at the start of the activation were high, since the room had a previous setpoint of 24°C. Therefore, the HVAC still needed to provide some power to reach the new setpoint and decrease the temperature of the room. Due to the reduced cooling power provided by the HVAC, the indoor temperatures were slightly higher during the activation and rebound periods. However, the differences were only minor and in both cases, the temperatures reached the same value a couple hours after the activation.
- Activation S2: the second event happened also on the first day but during the afternoon. In this case, unlike the previous activation, the HVAC turned completely off. Since the HVAC had provided cooling during the whole day, the indoor temperature at the beginning of the period was 22°C. Therefore, when the aggregator forced a setpoint of 23.5°C, the HVAC could turn off since no more cooling was needed.
- Activation S3: the third activation took place at 12:00 of the second day. In this case, similarly to S2, the HVAC turned off during the activation. However, during midday the solar radiation was significantly higher (notice that the HVAC was working at almost maximum power in the base case) and therefore, the indoor temperature increased sharply during this S3 activation. For that reason, once the activation command was over, the HVAC had to turn on at maximum power to achieve the daily setpoint of 22°C. It took a few hours until the indoor temperatures of the aggregator case reached the same value as the base case.
- Activation S4: a similar behavior was seen for this activation as for the S1 that took place at the same hour. The HVAC reduced the consumption, but only a small percentage. This shows that thermal activations in the morning were less effective, as the indoor temperatures were higher at the beginning of these activations (as explained in S1).
- Activation S5: this activation is similar to the S2. The HVAC turned off during the activation and the temperatures increased compared to the base case. For this reason, the rebound effect was noticeable, as an important cooling power was needed after the activation, to achieve the 22°C setpoint.

Figure 6. Results of Scenario 1 - Residential (summer)

Regarding the winter case, the results are shown in Figure 7 and the activation received in Table 4. In this case also 5 activations were received. However, two of them searched for a higher impact as the temperature setpoint was decrease in -2°C , unlike the other three where the decrease was -1.5°C . In this case, the duration of the activations were also 30 or 60 minutes and they took place in the morning midday or afternoon.

Period	Activation	Setpoint	Day	Start	Duration
Winter	W1	20.5°C (-1.5°C)	1	08:00	30 min
	W2	20.5°C (-1.5°C)	1	18:30	30 min
	W3	20.5°C (-1.5°C)	2	12:00	1 h
	W4	20°C (-2°C)	3	08:00	1 h
	W5	20°C (-2°C)	3	18:00	1 h

Table 4. Activations received for Scenario 1 - Residential (winter)

- Activation W1: this activation was the first one that did not create a reduction in the HVAC consumption. As discussed to the summer case, early in the morning the indoor temperatures are similar to the night thermostat setpoint (19°C for the winter). In this W1 activation, the aggregator defined a setpoint of 20.5°C. The difference between setpoint and indoor temperature of 1.5°C was high enough to force the HVAC to run at maximum power. In order to reduce the HVAC consumption, the setpoint defined would have had to be lower and closer to the indoor temperature of 19°C.
- Activation W2: in this case, we see that the HVAC turned off due to the decrease of 1.5°C on the setpoint imposed by the aggregator. This fact produced a minor decrease in the indoor temperature that was recovered to the same values of the base case an hour after the end of the activation (when the rebound period ends).
- Activation W3: this activation was also not successful in reducing the consumption. In this case, the HVAC was turned off when the aggregator sent the activation and therefore could not reduce its consumption.

Figure 7. Results of Scenario 1 - Residential (winter)

- Activation W4: in this activation, we see the characteristic features that have already been discussed for early morning activation (S1 and S4), which are a slight reduction of HVAC power and an important rebound effect.
- Activation W5: this activation follows a similar behaviour as activation W2. The HVAC turned off during the event, barely affecting the indoor temperatures, which went back to the normal base case levels after the rebound period.

Figure 8 provides a representation of the change in power during the activations and the rebounds. The power change refers to the difference in power consumed between aggregator and base case, with respect to the base case consumption (see Eq. 4 and 5). Looking at the power reduction during the activations (green plots) it can be appreciated the two events (W1 and W3) where the same consumption was measured in the base case and aggregator case. As previously, discussed, the activations that took place early in the morning (S1, S4 and W4) where the ones that created the lowest decrease in the consumed power. Regarding the rebound periods (red plots), a higher variability can be observed. In fact, in some cases (S2, W2 and W3) the consumption during the rebound periods, decreased and in others, it exceeded 100% (S5 and W5).

Figure 8. Power change during activations and rebound periods for Scenario 1 - Residential

4.2. Scenario 2 – Prosumer

Figure 9 shows the results for the Scenario 2 – Prosumer. On top, the power balance for the base case is shown with energy consumptions on the positive direction (load consumption, battery charge, energy exported to the grid) and generations in the negative one (PV generation, battery discharge and energy imported from the grid). The first thing to highlight is that the laboratory battery does not follow any setpoints between -1500 and 1500W. For this reason, the battery only charged or discharged in specific moments of the test. In addition, the battery

carried out two security charges from the grid, which correspond to the highest grid consumptions, marked as G1 and G2.

Middle and lower plots of Figure 9 show the battery power and SoC, respectively, for base and aggregator case. Regarding the activations received, as shown in Table 5, three activations were received, one for each day. Two of them lasted 1h and forced a 0W setpoint on the battery, not allowing it to charge or discharge. The third event imposed a discharge of 2kW for 30 minutes.

Activation	Setpoint	Day	Start	Duration
1	0 W	1	18:30	1 h
2	0 W	2	14:00	1 h
3	-2000 W	3	20:00	30 min

Table 5. Activations received for Scenario 2 – Prosumer

- Activation 1: the first activation took place during the afternoon of the first day, at the same time as the grid charge G1 was expected to take place. The aggregator detected this event and decided to postpone the grid charge by imposing a setpoint of 0W on the battery for 1h. Once the activation was over, the battery performed the grid charge. Notice that, in this case, the defined rebound period of 1h is not enough to capture the consumption increase after the activation. In fact, the consumption increase was noticeable once the battery finished the grid charge in the base case, which happened around the end of the defined rebound period.
- Activation 2: in this case, like Activation 1, the aggregator postponed the second grid charge G2. Besides shifting the grid charge, we see another effect caused by this activation. While the battery was performing the grid charge in the aggregator case, the base case battery, that had already charged from the grid, was able to provide energy to the load. For this reason, the SoC at the end of the second day was lower for the base case than the aggregator case. However, the energy that the battery did not discharge in the aggregator case during the second day, was stored and used to cover the load in the morning of the third day. In this third day, the battery in the base case discharged from 50% to 20% SoC and in the aggregator case from 65% to 20% SoC.

These differences can also be seen by looking at the power imported from or exported to the grid. Figure 10 shows the difference in the exported power (black) and imported power (blue). The difference is calculated as the power in the aggregator case minus the base case. Thus, positive values represent increases due to the aggregator and negative values decreases. We can see how for Activation 1 and 2 the imported power was reduced during the activations and increased afterwards, when the battery was allowed to charge from the grid. In addition, as previously discussed, the additional energy discharged during the third day, created a peak of imported power reduction.

Figure 9. Results of Scenario 2 - Prosumer

- Activation 3: during this activation, the aggregator imposed a discharge of 2kW on the battery for 30 minutes, which was used to supply the load. For this reason, the imported power from the grid is reduced during the Activation 3 and the surplus energy from the battery is exported to the grid (see Figure 10).

Figure 10. Imported and exported power difference for Scenario 2 - Prosumer, calculated as the power in the aggregator case minus the base case

Finally, Figure 11 shows the power change during activations and rebound periods. All activations managed to reduce the power consumption, with Activation 3 being the most effective. Regarding the rebound periods, for Activations 1 and 2, they range between 9 and 27%. However, as previously discussed, the effects of the activations can be seen hours after the activation end. For this reason, the rebound effect for Activation 3 was not noticeable the hour after the event, but it is likely that it would have been seen later on.

Figure 11. Power change during activations and rebound periods for Scenario 2 - Prosumer

5. Discussion

To evaluate the impact of the activations received from the aggregator, the resulting KPIs, shown in Table 6, are assessed.

n°	KPI	1 - Residential		2 - Prosumer
		Summer	Winter	
KPI1	Total energy consumption change	+2.00%	-2.56%	-0.20%
KPI2	Total energy cost change	+5.30%	-4.02%	0%
KPI3	Load reduction	-32.53%	-28.05%	-50.73%
KPI4	Rebound effect	+12.92%	+15.78%	+17.82%
KPI5	Reliability index	100%	100%	100%
KPI6	Thermal comfort level	0%	0%	-
KPI7	Self-consumption factor change	-	-	+0.39%

Table 6. KPI results of the developed scenarios

KPI1 shows that the total energy consumed during each test did not necessarily decrease as a consequence of the aggregator. For the Scenario 1 – Residential (summer), the consumed energy increased 2%. This is justified by the fact that the goal of the aggregator is not to reduce the consumption, but to solve specific constraints that may appear on the grid. Therefore, a higher energy consumption but at off-peak times can be beneficial.

Similarly, as can be seen from KPI2, the cost of the purchased energy did not always decrease in the aggregator case. In the Scenario 2 – Prosumer, it was the same and in the Scenario 1 – Residential (summer) it actually increased over +5%. The activations received may force the customer to consume energy at times where their tariff has a higher cost. Also, the cost can simply be higher because the amount of energy consumed increases. This fact highlights the importance of defining proper incentives so that the customers get an economic benefit from participating in flexibility actions.

KPI3 shows that on average, the aggregator managed to reduce the loads through the activations sent. In the Scenario 2 - Prosumer the loads were reduced around -50% and in the Scenario 1 – Residential, around 30%. However, as discussed previously, not all the activations reduced the power consumption. Two of the activations of Scenario 1 – Residential (activations W1 and W3) did not manage to reduce the power consumed (see Figure 8).

KPI4 shows that the rebound effect, measured the hour after each activation, created on average an increase in the consumption between 12 and 18%. However, it has been seen that the rebound effect is not always clear, and that in some activations the consumption after an activation decreased (see Figure 8). In addition, as has been seen for Scenario 2 – Prosumer, the activations for the battery created changes in consumption hours after the activation periods (see Figure 10).

The KPI5 has resulted in a value of 100% for all scenario developed, meaning that the communication between the flexibility platform of the laboratory and the aggregator was successful.

KPI6 gives an indicator of the increased discomfort that the user may have experienced because of the aggregator activations in Scenario 1 – Residential. The value of 0% for both summer and winter cases shows that the temperature did not go out of the comfort range during any of the activations or rebound periods. Therefore, the aggregator did not compromise the comfort of the consumer at any moment of the test.

KPI7 measures the change in the self-consumption factor of the consumer in Scenario 2 – Prosumer. A slight increase of 0.39% has been recorded, which is justified by last activation received, which forced the battery to discharge energy that otherwise would have been consumed from the grid (see Figure 10).

6. Conclusions

In this work, a microgrid laboratory has been integrated with an aggregation platform in order to build a platform for demand-side flexibility testing. The set-up allows to use the laboratory elements to experimentally assess the potential for flexibility of different assets in a more realistic way than through pure simulations.

Several elements from the laboratory, including real, virtual and emulated ones, have been used to define different customer types and test their interaction with the aggregator. In particular, a HVAC unit and a battery from a PV self-consumption system have been used to provide flexibility. The scenarios developed showed how these assets can be a reliable source of flexibility, as long as the activations sent by the aggregator are correct. In terms of the customer impact, the only negative effect has been an increase in the cost of electricity in some cases, which can be counteracted with adequate incentives from the aggregator.

Based on this work, new scenarios including different assets, customers and activation types are expected to be tested. Such an experimental approach can contribute to increase the knowledge on demand-side flexibility which will then allow stakeholders to understand the impact of DR on the customers and consequently help the aggregators to define strategies for the real-life dispatch of DR assets.

Declaration of Competing Interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

Acknowledgements

Cristina Corchero is a Serra Hunter Fellow.

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